

QUESTIONS OF STUDYING VERBS OF MOVEMENT AND DISPLACEMENT IN THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *In this thesis article, the author thoroughly investigates the issues of using action verbs in Uzbek and English , providing a wealth of insights and perspectives.*

Keywords: action verbs, Uzbek linguistics, lexical-semantic groups, complex semantic content.

Introduction

Verbs in the Uzbek language and their form of expression are often objects of research (Shakurova M.&Giniyatullina L., 2023), (Salakhova R. & Giniyatullina L., 1991). The thematic group of this part of speech also requires separate careful analysis. In Turkic linguistics, the problem of lexical-semantic groups of verbs was first covered in the work of the famous Turkologist N.K. Dmitriev. He identified the following groups of verbs: verbs of speech, verbs of thinking, verbs of motion, and

verbs of action (Dmitriev N. K., 1962). The author indicated two semantic groups of verbs of motion:

- 1) verbs denoting the direction of movement;
- 2) verbs denoting the method of movement [Ibid.

In his work, E.V. Sevortyan indicates verbs of vertical and horizontal movement (Sevortyan E. V., 1962).

The verbs of motion of the Turkic languages are also devoted to the essay of E.R. Tenishev, in which rich factual material is collected, and valuable theoretical conclusions are made. In particular, the author provides an original semantic classification of Turkic verbs. According to semantic features, verbs of motion are divided into two groups:

1) verbs of general meaning and 2) verbs of specific motion. The first group includes four verbs that are antonymous in meaning, and the second, based on specific features, is divided into three groups: verbs indicating:

- a) the method of movement;
- b) overcoming an obstacle in movement;
- c) the speed of movement (Tenishev E. R., 1961). Yu. V. Psyanchin, in his

work, divides verbs of motion into two groups:

- 1) verbs of directed movement;
- 2) verbs of undirected movement;
- 3) verbs of rest are subdivided into subcategories (Ganiev F. A., 1963).

In Uzbek linguistics, lexical and semantic groups of verbs are indicated in the work of Usmanov A., who identifies eight groups of verbs:

- 1) verbs of action; 2) verbs of motion;
- 3) verbs of state;
- 4) verbs denoting psychological state and physiological action;
- 5) verbs of sensory perception;

6) verbs of thinking;

7) verbs of speech; 8) call verbs (Turaeva D. G., 1986).

F. A. Ganiev identifies 11 lexical-semantic groups of verbs, including verbs of motion (Ganiev F. A., 1997). Verbs of motion are also identified in the works of Tanishev I. and F. Sergeeva (Sergeeva N. N., 1970).

In English, two terms denote movement by verbs: verbs of motion and verbs of displacement.

In some cases, they are used as equivalent, in others – as unequal, and sometimes these two concepts are combined into one term, calling them verbs of motion-displacement. As is known, the concepts of “movement” and “displacement” are unequal. It would be appropriate to include verbs expressing any movement in general in the semantically broad and quantitatively unlimited group of verbs of motion. Movement in space is a particular case of movement, and verbs such as “to go” – to walk, to run, to run, etc. – show the unidirectional and multidirectional movement of an object or subject. Based on this, in our opinion, the verbs of this group should be called by the term “verbs of motion.”

Verbs of motion in the Uzbek language mean movement, motion in the space of various persons, objects, natural phenomena, etc. For example, *Hoshim biroz turdi-da, so'ng musiqa va qo'shiq ovozi tomon kelayotgan uyga qarab yurdi* (Zainishev A. A., 1982). Hashim stood for a while and entered the house, where songs and the accordion sound were heard. It bir necha bor sakradi. The dog jumped up several times.

As we can see, all these verbs denote movement in space. They differ in meaning: some are limited in nature, that is, they denote an action that occurred only once (sakradi (jumped), *qarab yurdi* (entered), etc.), some are long-term, multiple actions (*kela turib* (goes), etc.). Verbs of movement in the Uzbek language can be divided into the following semantic groups:

1. Verbs denoting the general concept of movement. Such verbs have the meaning of continuous, undirected movement in space: *yurmoq* (to walk), *kesib o'tmoq* (to cross), *iyarmoq* (to become attached), *harakatlanmoq* (to move), *o'tmoq* (to pass). Such units mean universal movement that is not conditioned by any factors and is actively used in different styles of the Uzbek language.

2. Verbs denoting the direction of movement are the largest semantic group in quantity. Several subgroups can be distinguished within this group:

a) verbs of horizontal movement: *bormoq* (to go), *kelmoq* (to come), *ketmoq* (to leave), *quvmoq* (to chase), *o'zmoq* (to go around), etc.;

b) verbs of vertical motion: *yiqilmoq* (to fall), *tushmoq* (to descend), *ko'tarilmoq* (to rise), *egilmoq* (to bend over), *cho'kmoq* (to sink), *yiqilmoq* (to fall), *egilmoq* (to bend over), etc.;

c) verbs of rotational motion: *aylanmoq* (to turn around), *burulmoq* (to turn around), etc.;

d) verbs directed inward or outward: *kirmoq* (to enter), *chiqmoq* (to leave), *qaytmoq* (to return), *kertmoq* (to let go), etc.;

e) verbs of multidirectional action: *yechilmoq* (to crumble), *chayqalmoq* (to oscillate), *ag'namoq* (to wallow), etc.

3. Verbs denoting the mode of motion. Such verbs indicate movement on different surfaces in space. These include the verbs *uchmoq* (to fly), *oqmoq* (to flow), *suzmoq* (to swim), *cho'milmoq* (to dive), etc. The number of such verbs in the ep language is limited.

4. Verbs denoting the speed of movement. They are divided into the following semantic subgroups:

a) verbs denoting fast movement: *yugirmoq* (to run), *chopmoq* (to run), *shoshilmoq* (to hurry), *oshiqmoq* (to hurry), *tashlanmoq* (to rush), etc.;

b) verbs denoting slow movement: *sekinlashuv* (to slow down), *qimirlamoq* (to stir), etc.; c) verbs denoting monotonous or aimless movement: *tebraluv* (to swing), *chayqaluv* (to swing), *silkinmoq* (to move), etc.

5. Verbs denoting the manner of movement indicate how the subject performs the movement: *o'rmalamoq* (to climb), *oqsoqlanmoq* (to limp), *sakrash* (to jump), etc.

6. Verbs denoting the beginning and end of movement. Any movement in space has its beginning, and it can be constant or can end at some point. For example, the verbs – *harakat qilmoq* (to set in motion) *qo'zg'olmoq* (to move) are characterized by the meaning of the beginning of movement. Moreover, the verbs *to'xtash* (to stop), *to'xtamoq* (to stop), *harakatsizlanmoq* (to become motionless) have the opposite meaning.

In addition to these verbs, the Uzbek language has two-valued verbs. There are a few of them. Such units include verbs like *yotmoq* (to lie down), *Optimo* (to sit down), and *turmoil* (to stand up).

Depending on what process the verb denotes – static or movement – it can denote both movement and state. The context determines the verb's meaning. For example, in this example, the verb *yotmoq* (to lie down) denotes movement.

In the Uzbek language, verbs of movement can also be expressed in analytical forms. In modern linguistics, the problem of analytical verbs is quite controversial. In his works, F. A. Ganiev classifies these verbs as analytical forms of the aspect category and identifies the following semantic groups of aspectuality: beginning, duration, repeatability, incomplete performance, effectiveness, and ending (Ganiev F. A., 1963). The monograph by E. R. Tanisheva also provides the same classification (Tenishev E. R., 1961). Psyanchin Yu. V. covered some problems of the aspect category in Tatar verbs, including a detailed study of analytical forms denoting the direction (orientation) of action in space (Gilazetdinova G.K., 2022).

Thus, verbs of motion in the Uzbek language have a complex semantic composition and can mean different motion characteristics. The context often determines their meaning.

In Uzbek fiction, verbs denoting the general concept of motion, verbs of horizontal motion, verbs denoting directed movements inward or outward, and two-valued verbs are used more often than others.

In fiction, many analytical forms are used to form the grammatical category of aspect. Such constructions are formed from adverbial participles ending in -up / -ep / -p, less often - in -y / I, -a / -a, and various auxiliary verbs. The latter role can also be played by verbs of motion such as *bormoq* (to go), *yurmoq* (to walk), *chiqmoq* (to go out), *kirmoq* (to leave), etc., which lose their basic semantics of movement and begin to denote various additional semantics: beginning or end, duration of action, etc. Such variants of analytical aspects are characteristic only of the Uzbek language.

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O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA HARAKAT FE'LLARI TADQIQI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tezisda muallif o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi harakat fe'llarining qo'llanilishi masalalarini o'rgangan va ma'lum bir qarashlar qilgan. Ikki til harakat fe'llarini badiiy asarlardagi harakat fe'llari orqali tahlil qilgan hamda hulosalar qilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: harakat fe'llari, o'zbek tilshunosligi, leksik-semantik guruhlar, murakkab semantic tarkib.